

With Regard to the Connection between Pedagogical Schools and High Schools in Teacher Training and Retraining in Vietnam

Asso. Pro and Dr. Truong Thi Bich¹, Dr. Nguyen Duc Khuong²

^{1,2} Researcher team of The University of Education - Hanoi National University

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 03 January 2023	In teacher training and retraining, the close connection between pedagogical schools and high schools is one of the important factors, which is not only meaningful in deciding the quality of trained teachers, but also meaningful in the professional development process of teachers themselves during the time they practice education in high schools.
Corresponding Author Truong Thi Bich	The article mentions measure to link pedagogical schools with high schools in developing professional competencies for teachers to meet the requirements of educational innovation in the current context in Vietnam. That is to build a legal basis between the pedagogical school and the high school in organizing students to practice pedagogy and retrain teachers; is to build a partnership in professional development for teachers; is to build relationships in the organization of practice improvement studies.
KEYWORDS: Profession development, pedagogical school, high school, connection, training and retraining.	

1. FOREWORDS

Facing the context of extensive international integration and meeting the requirements of the fundamental and comprehensive renovation of Vietnamese education in the direction of standardization and modernization, that the development of the teaching staff is considered a key stage, pedagogical universities need to put the task of training and professional development orientation for teachers as an important task and built in the strategic development roadmap of the universities. Accordingly, teacher training institutions need to closely associate with high schools in implementing this task of training and retraining because high school is educational institution using training products of a pedagogical school, is the address that affirms the advantages and disadvantages of a pedagogical school through the quality of teachers trained from the school. Recognizing the important significance of this practice, many scientists have been interested in research and have had really valuable research works in improving the quality of teacher training as well as supporting teachers in their professional development in high school.

The research work of Thomas (2003) states that the high school is the place of "product consumption" of the pedagogical school. That shows that the relationship between the high school and the pedagogical school is a supply-demand relationship [1]. During the initial stage of training at a pedagogical school, which prepares students to be qualified

to meet basic requirements in professional activities in high schools, the relationship between pedagogical schools and high schools is established by activities organized for trainee teachers to practice and teaching practice [2], [3]. The learning during the probationary period of a new teacher is considered a transitional period from studying at a pedagogical school with the stage of practicing as a full-time teacher. At this stage, teachers are still in the "teaching profession" learning stage. Learning takes place simultaneously in two main forms: (i) learning through experience performing the actual tasks of teachers at school under the guidance of experienced teachers; (ii) learning through regular training courses at the locality or organization responsible for professional development for new teachers [4], [5]. Participating in training for teachers in these classes can be lecturers of pedagogical schools, experts outside the school, education experts (from management levels or education and training centers).

In order to provide professional support measures for teachers, many studies have studied the current situation of teacher training in pedagogical schools, the ability to meet the practical requirements of general education of final year students and teachers as well as suggestions on measures to retrain teachers in the general education environment [6],[7]; draw on international experiences in teacher training as well as support new teachers graduating from countries with developed education [8],[9]. These are really valuable lessons

for the country's educational reform in the period of deep international integration. In addition, some preliminary studies have proposed measures to support teachers in the first years of working in high schools. [10], [11]. Some studies also study the current situation of students' needs during the pedagogical internship period in high schools as well as the "disparity", "difference" between teacher training institutions and high schools in teacher training [12], [13], from there, draw out the content that needs to be trained for students so that right after graduation they can confidently teach classes. In general, there have been many studies on the difficulties of teachers in the first years of teaching practice in high schools; inadequacies of students during the pedagogical internship period, from which initial measures have been proposed in teacher training and retraining. However, there are not many studies on the close relationship and the connection between pedagogical schools and high schools in training and professional development for teachers as well as the necessity and initiative of the pedagogical school in guaranteeing and maintaining the quality of teacher training. In fact, it is necessary to continue to have more in-depth studies on this issue to ensure the achievement of educational goals, especially in the process of reforming programs and textbooks implemented from the 2020-2021 school year.

2. CONTENT

Talking about the connection between the pedagogical school and the high school is talking about the relationship between the teacher training institution and the institution employing teacher. Pedagogical schools are the place to provide human resources, the place to "create products" - special products, and high schools are the "customers who consume products". High schools have the right to recruit teachers with solid professional competence, professional qualities and necessary pedagogical skills. Therefore, pedagogical schools need to follow the practical requirements of high schools in order to develop appropriate training programs and content, to provide generations of teachers to meet the teaching-educational requirements of high schools in the integration period. That is, the training of human resources in a pedagogical school with the use of such human resources in high schools must be a closed and interconnected process

2.1. Building a legal basis between pedagogical schools and high schools in organizing pedagogical internships for students and retraining teachers

The connection between pedagogical schools and high schools has become an issue of particular interest to researchers, policymakers and educational administrators in the era of globalization. This issue is considered as a hot spot to solve for education reform and teacher training in the implementation of reforming the general education program.

In the professional development of teachers, the relationship between pedagogical schools and high schools must take place in one or several aspects such as: (1) In teacher training and development, the most common of which is sending students to high schools to practice pedagogy so that they can have the best pedagogical capacity to help them not be surprised in the first years of teaching in high school and perform well in their assigned tasks; (2) In the matter of creating a link of responsibility for research and improvement of educational and training practice; (3) In management, quality assurance of teacher education and training. The responsible participation of each member, including pedagogical schools, general schools and educational management agencies at all levels, is a condition to ensure the quality and effectiveness of this connection and the performance of each member.

The connection between pedagogical schools and high schools in organizing students to practice pedagogy and retraining teachers, taking practical improvement in classrooms and high schools as a driving force, reflects the internal quality management relationship. So this connection should first be supported by the management of the Education sector. The Ministry of Education and Training must have documents stipulating responsibilities and guidelines for pedagogical schools and high schools in organizing internships for students as well as in retraining teachers. The materialization of this document must confirm that the instructor's involvement in pedagogical practice needs to be assessed and recognized from various levels such as: (1) At the national level, this criterion must be included in the professional standards of teachers and professional standards of pedagogical teachers; (2) At the Department level, based on the standards in the professional standards, teachers must organize assessment and classification of schools, administrators, and teachers in completing the task of guiding and supporting students in teaching practice; (3) At the institutional level, teachers' achievements are recognized through a system of diplomas and certifications related to their salaries and bonuses.

2.2. Building a partnership between pedagogical schools and high schools in professional development for teachers

The partnership here represents the roles, responsibilities, and work contents of both the pedagogical school and the high school. Here, the concept of teacher development is used to refer to the learning efforts of teachers to perfect the knowledge, especially the skills that are lacking and weak in the training process at the pedagogical school; to improve their professional capacity, better respond to the requirements set out in the educational activities of the school, especially in the educational renovations. Professional development for teachers does not mean that they go to school to get a higher degree than the standard required for teachers to teach at a certain level. It should be

emphasized that the inevitable consequence of professional development for teachers is the improvement of their professional competence; help students learn the best, leading to the quality of the school's education will be improved. Thus, the concept of professional development for teachers emphasizes qualitative rather than quantitative aspects and refers to the actual effectiveness of teacher development. It shows that professional development for teachers is associated with their continuous learning, from initial training at pedagogical schools, to learning in the stage of being a mere apprentice (apprenticeship phase) and regular training in the process of working at the school, for the quality goals of teachers in particular and of education in general

2.2.1. Stages of professional development of teachers in high schools

- In the initial training stage, students are brought down to the high school to familiarize themselves with school activities, observe the activities of school members such as students, teachers, students' parents, community, other employees...; learn and practice doing the work of a teacher in a real environment under the guidance and management of head teachers, subject teachers and school administrators. Trainee teachers gain a lot of knowledge, skills and experience in teaching and education from activities in high schools. It can be said that high school is a place where trainee teachers learn in practice, about practice and to practice what they have learned in theoretical lessons. High school is considered as a place to help trainee teachers learn through contact with the school's vivid reality, by exploring, experiencing and practicing vocational skills on the basis of equipped theory, i.e. combine theory and practice. Therefore, it is necessary to understand more fully about the role of high schools in teacher training, avoiding seeing high schools as just a field of practice and fieldwork of a pedagogical school. Therefore, the high school participates in initial training as a partner to help trainee teachers have skills and experience in professional activities in practical situations.

- In the next stage, teachers with learning work in the probationary period of being a mere apprentice are considered as a transitional period from studying at a pedagogical school with the stage of practicing as a full-time teacher. At this stage, young teachers are still in the stage of learning "to be a teacher". Learning takes place at the same time in two main forms: (1) Learning through experience performing the actual tasks of a teacher in a high school under the guidance of an experienced teacher; (2) Learning through periodical training courses organized by the pedagogical school, and the pedagogical school is responsible for coordinating with the high school teachers to make up for the shortcomings, "occupational errors", "the defects" in training for young teachers; helping young teachers add more knowledge and skills, step by step self-improvement to be able to meet the requirements of the classroom teacher.

- In the period of retraining and professional development for teachers at high schools, young teachers play the same role as other teachers. The connection between the pedagogical school and the high school mainly takes place in thematic and regular training activities. The participation of university lecturers in professional development for teachers is mainly as an expert on a specific subject or issue. And the issue of teacher training is to develop the capacity of teachers in general, and young teachers in particular, to respond to new requirements brought about by changes in society, education, and schools. This is a form of advanced training for teachers not only to update information and new tasks but also to provide relevant new scientific knowledge and new educational research results.

2.2.2. At the pedagogical school: Teacher training always adapts to the innovation of education

- Teacher training programs development in the direction of linking with the general education program, training qualified and capable teachers to effectively operate the new general curriculum

The mission of the pedagogical school is extremely important when laying the first brick for students' professional knowledge of teaching; equipping future generations of teachers to become citizens with a world-view, bravery and ambition, dedicated to the teaching profession. The teacher training program should be closely linked with the educational program in high schools. One of the requirements and tasks of the overall general education program is to promote learners' capacity, effectively apply knowledge into practice, to meet the national industrialisation and modernisation process. Therefore, the teacher training program at pedagogical schools needs to be adjusted accordingly in order to provide outputs for the education sector - to train teachers with sufficient qualifications and capacity to effectively operate the new general education program. Pedagogical schools in particular and teacher training institutions in general need to identify four orientations for teacher education and training programs in the changing context: Education focuses on capacity development; integrated learning; open the university to society; assessment promotes learning. Teacher training in the current integration context is one of the urgent and vital tasks that determine the quality of education and the fundamental and comprehensive renovation of Vietnamese education. To be able to accomplish those tasks, teacher training institutions when developing educational programs need to focus on qualities and competencies to meet the requirements of an ever-changing education. With a system of basic competencies, teachers will be able to train Vietnamese high school students to become citizens of the 21st century, ready to go into working life or further study in an ever-changing world. It will be a place to provide competitive human resources in the period of integration and

globalization, contributing to enhancing Vietnam's position in the international arena.

According to the above spirit, teacher training programs at pedagogical schools need to be changed and adjusted in the direction of increasing practicality; develop professional capacity, pedagogical capacity, capacity to cope with arising situations. It is necessary to combine serial and parallel training models because each type of model has advantages and disadvantages, and has its own inadequacies and advantages; controls the output graduation standard; develops standards of quality inspection system; enhances students' scientific research,...

- Professional development for students in the field environment

The professional development for students must be closely linked with the general education environment. During the four years of study in the pedagogical school, students learn a lot of knowledge from Psychology, Education, National Defense Education, Physical Education, Logic to specialized subjects, subjects on Physics Theory and methods of teaching the subject. However, the theoretical content is much but the practical content is lacking. Therefore, it is necessary to build a balanced and reasonable training program between basic subjects and subjects on vocational training and pedagogical skills development. It is necessary to reduce the theoretical and academic nature of the subjects in order to increase the practicality, and to stick more closely to the curriculum in high schools. Most students, when they go to high school for internships, realize that the Psychology and Education subjects trained in pedagogical schools have not helped them much in grasping students' psychology, in handling teaching and educational situations, in homeroom work, in organizing collective activities, in making a work plan,...

Most students believe that when they go to high school, they begin to have a full and clear image of a teacher. The 5-week pedagogical internship period is just enough for them to "imitate" and "follow" but not yet confident enough to actively and creatively perform the tasks of teaching and learning in high school. Students must be visualized earlier than the functions and duties of a high school teacher in practice in order to have a training orientation as soon as they enter the pedagogical school. And until they graduate from school, they can quickly start working right from the first days of teaching. To develop a career for students in the field environment, it must:

* *Organize for students to go to high school right from the first year of study*

Teaching is a profession, so the learning process cannot be separated from the reality of teaching. Right from the first year, students should be arranged for 1 to 2 weeks of contact with the high school. The aim is to familiarize students with general education as teachers. During these early weeks, students only heard local education reports. Students will

gradually understand the position and role of teachers in teaching as well as homeroom work. From the initial observations, students will determine for themselves the training requirements to become an official teacher. In the second year, students continue to go to high school, but the content is changed that they attend time to understand the requirements and how to conduct a lesson. Students participate in the task of homeroom to understand the content that needs to be done and how to do it. Participating in understanding the psychology of students, participating in finding measures to educate students in general and special students (black sheep) in particular. With these contents, students initially trained some necessary qualities and competencies of teachers: confidence in front of students, awareness of their position and role in the school, in help and educate students. Initially grasp the requirements, content and how to perform professional operations. In the third year, students go to high school to do homework, attend class and prepare lessons to trial teach some lessons. In this third year, students have basically grasped the teaching and educational activities in high schools, and envisioned the missions and tasks that the high school teachers have to undertake. And in the fourth and final year, students go to high school for the final internship. During this time, students have accumulated for themselves professional skills, professional operations, teaching-education skills, etc. from the previous stages of high school. The method of organizing students to go to high school from the first year will contribute to the training of teachers with solid professional qualifications, pedagogical capacity, professional skills, love for the profession, etc. meeting the requirements of reforming general education.

* *Invite experienced high school teachers to class, teaching as a model for students in the process of regular pedagogical training*

As those who are directly involved with general education, more than anyone else, high school teachers are the best communicators of knowledge from the program to students. And they are also the best handlers of pedagogical situations that occur in the educational process. Before sending students to high schools to practice pedagogy, the pedagogical school should have a plan to invite high school teachers to talk and exchange with students about teaching and learning activities in high schools, about experience in class, experience as head teacher,...

* *Pedagogical schools send lecturers to high schools to supervise students' practical activities*

As the person who directly develops the program, organizes teaching - professional training for future teachers, pedagogical lecturers need to understand the high school environment, accurately and objectively grasp the advantages and disadvantages of students in times of rubbing with the reality of that environment to adjust and supplement their teaching and educational plans.

* *Organize scientific seminars on teacher training with the participation of high school teachers*

Scientific seminars are a very good opportunity for pedagogical schools and high schools to connect in the following aspects: practically updating pedagogical science in the country and in the world; general qualifications of high school teachers; their advantages and disadvantages; infrastructure conditions; qualifications, psychological aspects of high school students. From this connection, the pedagogical school can receive to improve, reform and innovate teaching contents, programs and methods; bring learning activities at pedagogical schools close to teaching activities in high schools

2.3. Building a collaborative relationship between pedagogical schools and high schools in organizing practical improvement research

The organization of research on practical improvement is organized by the pedagogical school in collaboration with the high school to carry out the task of educational research with various types of applied research towards practical improvement (mainly associated with the application of theories and theories into practice to improve the quality and effectiveness of education) which are more common and associated with reality in many issues, including professional development for young teachers.

First of all, in researches aimed at improving practice in high schools, research members of pedagogical schools and high schools jointly participate in research, discovery and solution of existing problems in the school in both management, teaching organization, and education of teacher. With research located in high schools and carried out by members of pedagogical schools and high schools together with a number of outside experts, it will bring many benefits. First of all, the results from the research will help high schools understand themselves, grasp the existing problems of teachers, and offer practical solutions to develop professional competence for teachers; therefore, the solutions given will be more realistic and feasible.

Furthermore, when high school teachers participate in research as practitioners-researchers (not as facilitators or informants), they contribute to schools like real owners. As a result, teachers become bolder, more confident and competent. On the other hand, working with research experts who are pedagogical lecturers, members of the high school will learn research and problem-solving skills. On the contrary, from the pedagogical school's side, when collaborating with high schools, they will better understand the reality of the school and get information and research results to enrich their understanding of high schools, thereby making improvements and additions to the content of teacher training in pedagogical schools

3. CONCLUSION

In the career of teacher training and retraining, a close connection between pedagogical schools and high schools is extremely necessary. The training process cannot be separated from the reality of high school. In contrast, the end of a 4-year training course is not the end of a teacher's "learning". Self-study and self-improvement to constantly improve the quality of teaching is a task that always accompanies teachers throughout their teaching life. And their reliable address is the pedagogical school, where there are researchers, leading scientists, teachers who are enthusiastic and responsible for the career of teacher training in particular and for the education reform in general.

In the process of teacher training and retraining, if this connection is done well, it is certain that students who graduate from school will be truly "pride" when bringing the latest and most advanced knowledge about the high school to practice teaching. And high school teachers also self-improve and perfect their professional capacity to continue to be good teaching examples meeting the requirements of modern society.

To provide society with qualified teachers to meet the new requirements of general education, and to collect information on the advantages and disadvantages of training products to help adjust the program training, content, training methods, etc., pedagogical schools need to be responsible for teachers, especially young teachers in continuing to provide them with professional training courses to update modern scientific information, to make up for the shortfalls and difficulties they encountered in the first years of teaching profession. This can only be done by linking pedagogical schools with high schools on the basis of a legal framework with specific partnerships. With the process of warranty and maintenance in teacher training, along with the building of quality training programs, effective training content, methods, and engagement with the high schools; it will train generations of teachers who are good in expertise, bravery, dynamic in pedagogy, perfect in personality, meeting the requirements of education - training reform in general and general education in particular

REFERENCES

1. Thomas, E. (2003). *Partnership and partnership change in teacher education*. Xem trong: Razdevšek-Pučko, C. (2006), *Partnership in teacher education: are we speaking the same language?* 31st Annual ATEE (Association of Teacher Education in Europe) Conference. www.pef.uni.lj.si.
2. Lampert, M. (2010). *Learning teaching in, from, and for practice: what do we mean?* Journal of teacher education 2010;61;21. www.jte.sagepub.com
3. ALTC (Australian Learning and Teaching Council), (2009). *Practicum partnership: exploring models of*

“With Regard to the Connection between Pedagogical Schools and High Schools in Teacher Training and Retraining in Vietnam”

- practicum organisation in teacher education for a standard-based profession*. Final report. VCDE, the University of Melbourne, RMIT university, Victorian institute of teaching. www.altc.edu.au
4. *The improvement of teacher qualifications in Singapore: Closely associated with on-the-spot training*.
[Http://etep.moet.gov.vn/tintuc/chitiet?Id=208](http://etep.moet.gov.vn/tintuc/chitiet?Id=208)
 5. *Experience the education system in Canada*, <http://www.baobinhphuoc.com.vn/content/trai/nghi-em-he-thong-giao-duc-o-canada-68745>.
 6. Nguyen Thi Kim Dung. *Current status of teacher training – viewed from the ability to meet the practical requirements of general education of final year students and young teachers*. Journal of Education and Society, issue 10 (68), October 2011, P. 13-15, ISSN 1859-3917.
 7. Dao Thi Oanh. *Young teachers' needs for pedagogical training content*. p. 81-88, Proceedings of the Scientific Conference *The improvement of pedagogical professional quality for students of pedagogical universities*. Hanoi National University of Education, 2010.
 8. Truong Thi Bich. *Some issues on professional development of teachers in Malaysia and Singapore and lessons for Vietnam*. Proceedings of the International Scientific Conference, 2017, p. 179-192.
 9. Tao Thi Hong Van. *The role of supporting young teachers in high schools in European countries*. Magazine "Teaching and Learning Today", issue 2/2018, P. 70-74.
 10. Truong Thi Bich. *The role of pedagogical universities in professional development for young teachers*. Science journal, Hanoi National University of Education, Volume 63, issue 2A, 2018. p. 23-32
 11. Tran Thi Yen. *Solutions to support professional activities of the pedagogical universities for young teachers in high schools*. Science journal, Hanoi National University of Education, Volume 63, Issue 217, p. 188-197
 12. Nguyen Thi Canh, 2010. *Listening to students' opinions when practicing pedagogy in high school*. Proceedings of the Scientific Conference *The improvement of pedagogical professional quality for students of pedagogical universities*. Hanoi. p.153-157
 13. Nguyen Thanh Thi. *From “theory” to “practice” and “train” – the gap needs to be shortened in teacher training*. Proceedings of the scientific conference *The improvement of pedagogical professional quality for students of pedagogical universities*, p. 260, 2010
 14. Nguyen Thi Kim Dung, 2017. *The development of professional capacity for young teachers in the form of on-the-spot learning through the internet*. Proceedings of the International Scientific Conference *The development of teachers to meet the requirements of education and training innovation*. Hue University, p. 78-86
 15. Dinh Quang Bao, 2011. *Report on the reality of teacher training in Vietnam*. Vietnam Peace and Development Fund